

Disease Outbreak and Prevention Control in Coldwater Fisheries

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Abstract

Aquaculture, particularly in the Coldwater fisheries of the Indian Himalayas, faces significant challenges from various diseases affecting both exotic and indigenous fish species. This article reviews the types and impacts of diseases—such as viral, bacterial, fungal, and parasitic—on Coldwater fish populations, highlighting their detrimental effects on production. Prevention strategies including pond regulation, rearing management, fish seed disinfection, and pond treatments are discussed. Environmental considerations and disease diagnosis methods are also addressed, emphasizing the importance of sustainable aquaculture practices amidst growing concerns over water quality and disease management. Effective disease control measures involving therapeutic treatments are outlined to mitigate the spread and impact of diseases in Coldwater aquaculture.

Keywords: Coldwater aquaculture, fish diseases, disease prevention, aquaculture management, environmental impact, sustainable practices

Introduction

Aquaculture is the fastest-growing animal food sector and will continue to expand to meet the global food demands. Along with this growth, aquaculture industry is increasingly threatened by diseases, caused by bacteria, viruses, fungi, oomycetes and parasites. Coldwater fisheries play a crucial role in Indian aquaculture production. Today, the available technologies allow the culture of a number of exotic and indigenous Coldwater fish species in the Indian Himalayas. The most common exotic species are rainbow trout, brown trout, common carp, while the indigenous fish are: mahseers (*Tor putitora* and *Tor tor*), and schizothoracines (*Schizothorax ichthyosocinus*, *S.*

progastus, *Schizothorax richardsonii*, *S. niger* and *S. curvifrons*). Among these *Tor putitora*, *S. progastus* and *S. richardsonii* are preferred because of their wide range of distribution in the Indian Himalayas. Fish pathogens can have detrimental effect on aquaculture production. Incidence of diseases in Coldwater aquaculture sector has been a matter of grave concern and due to the lack of a facility for disease diagnosis this work remained unattended for quite a while (Pande et al., 2012). In this article we discuss about the disease outbreak and prevention methods to control it. We can classify the disease outbreak into infection, invasive and disease due to physical and environmental stress.

Infectious Diseases

Infectious diseases are mainly caused by viruses, bacteria, fungi, or unicellular algae ("ichthyomicrobial diseases") e.g. bacterial enteritis, bacterial gill rot, and bacterial erythema. Infectious diseases account for 60 percent of the production loss. There are three stages in the course of infectious diseases: a latent period, a symptomatic period, and an attacking period. There are two types of infections: pure (one causative

agent) and mixed (two or more pathogens on a single fish). Likewise, there can be two sources of infection: primary and secondary. A primary infection originates within the pond. The pathogen may infect the fish directly or through the discharge of pathogenic agents into the water. Occasionally, "healthy" fish may act as disease carrier and an outbreak of disease may occur under certain conditions. A secondary infection originates outside the pond. The disease occur in Cold water has been listed on table (Bhat, R. .et al 2023)

S.no	Disease	Aetiological agent	Susceptible age group	Clinical signs
Bacterial Disease				
1	Lactococcosis	Lactococcus garvieae	All age groups	Hyperacute haemorrhagic septicaemia
2	Motile Aeromonas Septicaemia (MAS)	Aeromonas hydrophila	All age groups	Haemorrhagic septicaemia
3	Rainbow trout fry syndrome (RTFS)	Flavobacterium psychrophilum	Fry	Loss of balance, Spiralling swimming, drowsiness, hyperexcitability, bleeding and death
4	Columnaris disease/ Saddle-back disease	Flavobacterium columnare	All age groups	Lesions at the base Resembling a 'saddle- back'.
5	Cold-water disease (CWD)	Flavobacterium psychrophilum	All age groups	Loss of fin tip Integrity. In the peduncle region, there may be darkening of the skin colour
6	Bacterial gill disease	Flavobacterium sp.	Mostly fry and fingerling	Lethargy gasping for air, fish aggregation near the inlet of the tank
Viral disease				
1	Infectious hematopoietic necrosis (IHN)	Infectious hematopoietic necrosis virus (IHNV)—Fish Rhabdovirus	Fish under 2 months old tend to be the most vulnerable to the virus in both natural and artificial infections	Characterised by the necrosis of eosinophilic granular cells in the submucosal layer of the intestinal wall, which leads to trailing faecal casts
2	Viral haemorrhagic septicaemia (VHS) Aquabirnavirus	Fish Rhabdovirus—Viral haemorrhagic septicaemia virus (VHSV)	Younger fish are more vulnerable, and fish older than 6 months appear to be resistant	Necrosis in the kidney and spleen regions
3	Infectious	Infectious	Fry and post-smolt	Milky mucous

	pancreatic necrosis (IPN)	pancreatic necrosis virus (IPNV)		substance in the digestive tract and presence of McKnight cells
Parasite Disease				
1	White spot disease	Ichthyophthirius multifiliis	Fry and fingerlings	White pinhead-sized patches appear in the epidermis and gills
2	Costiasis	Costia necatrix	All age groups	The skin of the fish develops a light grey-blue film, and more severely affected body sections display red patches
3	Trichodiniasis	Trichodina, Trichodinella and Tripartiella	Common in young fish	Appearance of tiny red dots on gills
4	Gyrodactylosis	Gyrodactylus salaris	All age groups	Excess mucus secretion, gill filament breakage and haemorrhagic lesions in the gills
5	Black spot disease	Diplostomum sp.	Fry and fingerling commonly affected	Each fish has a unique pattern of spots, ranging in size from 1 to 2 mm, depending on the species
6	Eye disease of rainbow trout	Digenetic trematode (metacercaria)	Adult trout	Cataracts, lens displacement and degeneration, cortical fibre liquefaction and eventually blindness
7	Argulosis	Argulus sp.	All age groups	Localised reddish patches on the external body surface
8	Whirling diseases	Myxobolus cerebralis	Small fry and fingerlings	Imbalance and loss of homeostasis leading to erratic swimming

Prevention measure from disease outbreak Pond regulation

Fish production may be increased, illness can be avoided, and environmental conditions can

be improved via pond control. Pond control has two primary components: disinfection and pruning.

Rearing management

The day-to-day maintenance of the pond, including replenishing supplies, feeding, preventing illnesses, etc., should be left to a trustworthy individual. It is best to follow the planned feeding protocol, which increases fish productivity and prevents illness. Variations in the quality of the water need to be closely monitored.

Fish seed disinfection

Disinfecting fish seeds can be done before stocking them or during their transfer. Cleaning of the feed, feeding platform, and equipment. Feeds that have gone bad or tainted might bring harmful microorganisms into the pond. Remaining food particles break down in the water, allowing harmful germs to grow quickly. Feeds must thus be kept in a dry, well-ventilated area. Long-term stored feed should not be used. Nets, buckets, dip nets, and other equipment used during the epidemic season need to be cleaned and sterilised after every use.

Pond treatment

One typical way of preventing illness is to spread chemicals around the entire pond. The pond has to be thoroughly cleaned and disinfected with 1 ppm potassium permanganate prior to seed stocking. Quicklime should be applied to degraded pond water to enhance it. This will lessen illness and enhance the quality of the water. After dissolving the quicklime pieces in a little amount of water, the mixture should be diluted, mixed, and sprayed uniformly over the pond.

Establishing a quarantine system

Geographic and climatic conditions can produce epidemic diseases in certain regions. However, as the freshwater farming industry develops rapidly and the transportation of fry and fingerlings among provinces becomes more frequent, local diseases are tending to spread. Quarantine work should now be emphasized. The transportation of diseased fish should be strictly prohibited.

Diagnosis

The fish must be alive or recently dead and the body must be kept damp. Methods of diagnosis include surveying the pond and examining the fish with the naked eye and microscopically.

Survey the diseased pond

Determine if the water source is seriously polluted. If it is, find the source of the pollution. Observe the behavior of the diseased fish and take an inventory of the rearing status (pond clearing, stocking density, feeding, preventive methods, and mortality, etc).

How to cure a diseased fish?

In order to effectively control the health problem, desired dose of therapeutics could be given in three ways e.g. (i) adding medicine in the water (ii) Through feed (iii) through injection. First method is again divided into flush, dip, bath and pond treatment.

Flush Treatment: A higher concentration of chemical is added at the inlet or incoming water site and allowed to pass through the tank. Uniform distribution of chemical depends on the flow of water.

Dip Treatment: In this method fishes are collected by net from the tanks or nurseries and dipped for 1-3 minutes in high dose of medicine and released back in tanks. In this process, attached parasites detach from the body and get killed. Dip treatment is extremely useful in small fry and fingerlings facilities.

Bath Treatment: Employed in small experimental tanks under controlled conditions and after adding chemical/medicine left for specified time. The fishes are kept under observation and as soon as fish shows stress symptoms, either fresh water is added or fishes are taken out from the tanks and released in freshwater.

Pond Treatment: In bigger grow out fish ponds smaller dose of chemical/medicine is used. This method although widely used however before application of medicine economic return of the fish pond should also be taken care

Conclusion

The sustainable development of Coldwater aquaculture in the Indian Himalayas necessitates robust strategies for disease prevention and management. The prevalence of infectious,

invasive, and environmental diseases underscores the importance of proactive measures such as pond disinfection, careful rearing practices, and thorough disease diagnosis. Environmental impacts from aquaculture effluents highlight the need for continuous monitoring and management to preserve water quality and ecosystem health. Moving forward, integrating these practices into aquaculture operations will be crucial for ensuring the long-term viability and productivity of Coldwater fisheries in the region.

Reference

1. Pandey, A., Mallik, S. K., Chandra, S and Pandey, N. N. (2012). Coldwater fish disease in India: Status and Strategies. DCFR Silver Jubilee Compendium on Coldwater Fisheries. Pp. 83 88.
2. ICAR – DCFR guidelines of preventive measures for fish disease and major fish disease in Coldwater Chauhan, R & Arya, Priyanka. (2020). COLDWATER FISH FARMING.
3. Bhat, R. A. H., Mallik, S. K., Tandel, R. S., & Shahi, N. (2023). An overview of cold-water fish diseases and their control measures. *Fisheries and Aquaculture of the Temperate Himalayas*, 255-283.

